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ABSTRACT

Knowledge Management (KM) principles recognize that it is important for organizations to "know what they know." Are the concepts of knowledge management (KM) applicable to colleges and universities? All institutions inherently store, access, and deliver knowledge in some manner and educational institutions are no exception. However, although some examples exist, the use of KM in education is the exception rather than the rule. Knowledge management is a new field, and experiments are just beginning in education. This short paper explores how KM practices might be useful in a technology education setting.

KEYWORDS: Data, Information, KM(Knowledge Management),organization development.

1. INTRODUCTION

All the institute and organization use Knowledge Management (KM) concept in the beginning of 1990. Knowledge management system increase the value of knowledge. There are 3 basic elements present here those are creating a knowledge, broadcasting of the knowledge and purpose of the knowledge. Knowledge is also helpful for economic purpose of any organization such as capital, materials, machineries, and properties. Knowledge used by people for making decision and other actions. Knowledge can fragment into two parts- the first one is tacit knowledge and second is explicit knowledge. Tacit knowledge is subjective or experimental knowledge that cannot be expressed in words and explicit knowledge can be expressed in words. Organizational culture, technological tools and human beings are the key elements required for managing knowledge more effectively for better education delivery in time phased manner. Many knowledge management techniques available in present. Many institutes and organization participate for implementing KM principles, methods, practices or tools. According to Karl Sveiby [1] defined Knowledge Management as, "**The art of creating value from an organization intangible assets.**" And Davenport and Prusak [2] defined Knowledge Management as, "**KM is concerned with the exploitation and development of the knowledge assets of an organization with a view to furthering the knowledge objectives.**" Knowledge management improves the responsiveness by monitoring and incorporating lessons learned from the experiences of colleagues, student evaluations, and corporate or other constituent input and it also reduce the time for learning . Knowledge is deliberate as a capital which helps in increasing productivity, knowledge is a stability factor in an unstable and dynamic competitive environment and it involves the skills and the ability to act according to the rules and people use the knowledge for making decision as well as other actions. The key components of knowledge are experience, truth, complexity, judgment ,values and beliefs. Russell Ackoff, says that a systems theorist and professor of organizational change, the content of the human mind can be classified into five categories: data, information, knowledge, understanding and wisdom. Ackoff indicates that the first four categories relate to the past; they deal with what has been or what is known. Only the fifth category, wisdom, deals with the future because it incorporates vision and design. Knowledge derive from information and information derive from data in brief-

*Data is a collection of raw facts and figures.

*Information is data that makes a difference.

*Knowledge is a collection of data and information into ideas.

*Wisdom is knowledge of what is proper or reasonable : good sense or judgment and we can increase the quality and knowledge with the help of wisdom.

Knowledge Management

2. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

Knowledge

What is knowledge? Knowledge starts as data—raw facts and numbers—for example, the market value of an institution's endowment. Information is data put into context—in the same example, the endowment per student at a particular institution. Information is readily captured in documents or in databases; even large amounts are fairly easy to retrieve with modern information technology systems. Before acting on information, however, we need to take one more step. Only when information is combined with experience and judgment does it become knowledge. A popular framework for thinking about knowledge proposes two main types of knowledge: explicit and tacit [Polyani]. Explicit knowledge is documented information that can facilitate action. It can be expressed in formal, shared language. Examples include formulas, equations, rules, and best practices.

Explicit knowledge is:

- Packaged
- Easily codified
- Communicable
- Transferable

Tacit knowledge is know-how and learning embedded within the minds of the people in an organization. It involves perceptions, insights, experiences, and craftsmanship. Tacit knowledge is:

- Personal
- Context-specific

- Difficult to formalize
- Difficult to communicate
- More difficult to transfer

Most business actions require the guidance of both explicit and tacit knowledge.

* Knowledge Management

The term “Knowledge Management” (KM) is used to describe everything from the application of new technology to the harnessing of the intellectual capital of an organisation [Sallis and Jones]. It is not one single discipline; rather, it is an integration of numerous endeavours and fields of study. [Rowley] describes the term KM as follows: “Knowledge management is concerned with the exploitation and development of the knowledge assets of an organisation with a view to furthering the organisation’s objectives. The knowledge to be managed includes both explicit, documented knowledge, and tacit, subjective knowledge. Management entails all of those processes associated with the identification, sharing, and creation of knowledge. This requires systems for the creation and maintenance of knowledge repositories, and to cultivate and facilitate the sharing of knowledge and organisational learning. Organisations that succeed in knowledge management are likely to view knowledge as an asset and to develop organisational norms and values, which support the creation, and sharing of knowledge”. In brief, KM is the management of processes that govern the creation, dissemination, and utilisation of knowledge by merging technologies, organisational structures and people to create the most effective learning, problem solving, and decision-making in an organisation.

3. APPLYING KM IN EDUCATION

Using knowledge management techniques and technologies in higher education is as vital as it is in the corporate sector. As public, private, and for profit higher education institutions alike respond to the phenomenal growth of online courses, cyber colleges, and virtual universities, these same reasons to adopt KM apply. Knowledge management applications could benefit a number of university processes and services including:

- The research process,
- Curriculum development process,
- Student and alumni services,
- Administrative services,
- Strategic planning process

4. CHALLENGES TO IMPLEMENTING KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

There are obvious challenges to the implementation of KM. Some of them are the following:

- *Employees have no time for KM
- *Current culture does not encourage sharing
- *Lack of understanding of KM and benefits
- *Inability to measure financial benefits of KM
- *Lack of skill in KM techniques
- *Organization's processes are not designed for KM
- *Lack of funding for KM
- *Lack of incentives, rewards to share
- *Have not yet begun implementing KM
- *Lack of appropriate technology
- *Lack of commitment from senior management

Educational institutions would have to overcome these challenges in order to reap the benefits of KM.

5. NEED FOR KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

We are facing difficulties for finding the proper definition of knowledge. While we can speak about knowledge i.e. **KNOWLEDGE** is that which a person comes to believe and value on the basis of the systematic organized accumulation of information through experiences, communication as inference and another any insight into knowledge can be regarded as knowledge itself. Today knowledge management system is very essential for any

organization and institute for staying in global market. Many it companies also adopt the knowledge management system. In the present era we have a lot of new information and little time to learn it, so we need knowledge management system. This tool helps us access information very fast. At the end, we are capable to better deal with our customers' projects. Knowledge management is not only necessary for managing of knowledge, rather than it is also useful in knowledge era. Each organization knows the power of information. The main competition in the market between companies is that knowledge representation by employee. Knowledge management is the integration of culture, process and infrastructure. Knowledge management provides understanding of information that it create higher efficiency in employee throughout the company and this will save a lot of time.

6. CONCLUSION

Organization and institutes need awareness about knowledge management. We can increase the range of performance of any organization through knowledge management. The present era affected by new technologies and developments. At this time organization finds important information which is beneficial for company. When the company start they use knowledge. The biggest challenges in front of any institute is gathering information and how to manage knowledge. Knowledge management helps in increasing the financial value of the association and opportunities to all employee for enhancing their skills and experience

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